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Fire, Pestilence and the Extractive Economy: Cultural Policy after Cultural Policy.

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Abstract

Australia has witnessed long-standing cuts in the arts and culture federal budget. Most recently, the disappearance of the arts portfolio into a 'super-ministry' along with infrastructure, transport, regional development and communications further signals the lack of support, both ideologically through public rhetoric, and financially through (absent) support packages, the current federal government holds towards the arts and arts workers. This paper accounts for how such ideological fractures have underserved freelancers, casuals, temporary and part-time workers in the arts who missed out on the critical initial support packages, and how state governments were more willing to make up for this initial shortfall. This paper further accounts for how the federal government lacks the necessary understanding of working patterns of those engaged in creative occupations, and over emphasises funding bailouts for primary industry. This also has broader implications for how women are disproportionately impacted by sectors the federal government chooses to support.

Introduction

Australia, up until July 2020, had gained a reputation as one of the countries that had responded rapidly and effectively to the pandemic. The total number of Covid-19 deaths in Australia between March and August (around 200) was comparable to the *daily* death rate the UK government considered low enough to warrant relaxing their lockdown nationally in July. In late June however, the infection rate in Melbourne, Australia's second largest city, began to climb, provoking a near-total lockdown across the city, with Victorian state residents restricted from traveling to other parts of the country, then their home state, then beyond 5 kilometers from their house. At time of writing, and as in many other countries hit by a 'second wave', there has been a shift in tone, from planning a post-pandemic recovery to dealing anew with the immediate threat of the virus. If, at the beginning, "we can't go back to normal" was a plea to seize the opportunity for radical change, now it is more a statement of fact: Australia can't go back even if it wished. In this new uncertainty, as the landscapes of emergency and recovery blur into each other and stretch forward across time horizons nobody really anticipated, the self-confidence of the country has begun to waiver. What the government felt able to do in a short-term emergency – financial support for those

businesses and individuals impacted, with 'stimulus' for particular sectors – now looks more challenging. As with the Global Financial Crisis, the emergency response was first heralded as the return of Keynesianism; five months later, the Treasurer, outlining Australia's economic prospects, named Thatcher and Reagan as his guiding lights (Cooke, 2020; Eltham, 2020b). For the arts and cultural sector, a gloomy prospect turned darker.

By March 2020 when the Covid-19 crisis hit Australia, the country's Liberal/National Party ('Coalition') government had been in power for seven years, with a mandate until 2022. Four tenets of its approach to policymaking stood out: climate change denialism; budget austerity, labour deregulation and corporate tax cuts; a 'culture wars' rhetorical attack on elites and experts, with a downgrading of the public service's role in policy making and implementation; and, strongly tied to the first, a focus on an extractive economy, with the inevitable prioritization of the financial sector with which this is intertwined.

Some consequences of this became evident even in the face of the horrific 2019-2020 bushfire season that raged around the country in the months before Covid-19. The fires had millions of Australians weary, anxious and under threat from airborne pollutants before the year had barely begun. Covid-19 was not the first crisis this year to see Australians wearing N-95 masks in the streets and stores selling out. The Australian government had become one of the world's most noticeable climate change denialists, mirroring its position as the world's largest exporter of fossil fuels. After years of warnings and inaction, as the world watched the devastating bushfires, the government stuck to its denialism. The Prime Minister prevaricated, and his cheerleaders, including the Murdoch-owned NewsCorp media, blamed everything from arsonists to 'green tape' preventing controlled burn offs; everything except climate change. Though none of this changed their (non)action on climate change, Morrison was caught out of step with the 'quiet Australians' he had thanked for his recent, surprise, election victory. It was within this falling electoral popularity context that the Covid-19 emergency escalated globally. The Australian government acted quickly to close borders and, working alongside an emergency national cabinet that included the states and territories, imposed a lockdown. These actions set Australia apart from the UK and US, the two anglophone countries that would suffer the highest death rates in the developed world, putting it more in step with Canada and New Zealand.

This rapid lockdown response was accompanied by an equally rapid announcement of a 'stimulus package', which involved substantially increasing unemployment benefitsⁱ (*JobSeeker*) and introducing temporary payments (*JobKeeper*), paid via eligible businesses, including self-employed, for those whose work was adversely affected by the lockdown. The stimulus involved huge sums – over AU\$100 billion – now being found quite quickly, giving rise to those Keynesian hopes, ironically recalling the Coalition's deep-seated opposition to the relatively minor sums spent by Labor during the GFC. The government would, recalling Mario Draghi of the European Central Bank in 2012, 'do whatever it takes' (Tooze, 2018) - but without knowing at all what it would actually take, and indeed, what 'it' actually was. In the GFC it was the stabilization of the financial system and 'market confidence'; now it was getting back to a 'normal' which

might not return, and for many, was not necessarily an attractive option. As with all major crises, the longer it goes on, the greater the sacrifices, the more thoughts there are of not going back to normal. The current Australian government wants that normal back urgently, giving 'whatever it takes' a more sinister hue.

The Agony and the Advocacy

Accompanied by a photo of the entrance to the Australian Government's Office of Infrastructure, Transport, Regional Development and Communications, the 'super-ministry within which the 'Arts' had recently been buried, Laura Tingle, a respected economic and political journalist tweeted:

Just a reminder from a walk through Canberra this morning that 'Arts' didn't even make it into the name of the department. No wonder an \$111 billion industry is so easy to overlook. (O'Connor, 2020)

The Tweet exemplified much of the frustration within the cultural sector and its supporters with the lack of response by the Federal Government to its calls for help. The arts and culture sector, heavily dependent on live audiences, were amongst the first to be affected by the Covid-19 lockdown. Very quickly it emerged that many arts and cultural workers would not be eligible for the new *JobKeeper* allowance because they could not show 12 months *continuous* employment with *one* employer. As elsewhere, an arts and cultural sector - one that had been forced into increasingly precarious working conditions, donating the name 'gig economy' to the one third of the workforce in such employment (Eltham, 2020b) - was being missed by legislation predicated on long-since outdated workplace practices. People were also allowed to access their superannuation payments early, paying for their own 'bailout' at long term cost to themselves (Secombe, 2020). The cracks in this rapidly assembled piece of emergency legislation, through which many cultural workers fell, might initially be seen as accidental; but the continued silence in the face of mounting concern, followed by denial and prevarication, suggest a deeper ideological issue.

This was underlined by the fate of higher education, hard hit by border closures, whose employees were excluded from *JobKeeper*, with the government acting rapidly to close any loopholes that might be used by universities, even as job losses mounted. That Australia's fourth largest export industry was being left to swing, for what could only be ideological reasons (Economist, 2020; Cooke, 2020), did not bode well for an arts and cultural sector whose 'industry' credentials were dubious (O'Connor, 2020) and which was seen as either irrelevant or elitist. This has been a long time coming. Federal funding for arts and culture, including public broadcasting, has been falling since the Coalition came to power in 2013 (Meyrick et al, 2020). It already had one of the lowest percentages of GDP devoted to arts and culture in the OECD countries (Eltham, 2020a). The public broadcaster ABC, despite being seen to have reclaimed its position as an 'essential service' in the recent bushfire and Covid-19 crises, has been saddled with damaging cuts which an unrepentant Coalition government refused to walk back on in the midst of this crisis (so too the multicultural broadcaster SBS in the midst of *Black Lives Matter*).

Less obviously, and a deeper source of consternation, was the fact that twenty years of the cultural sector 'arguing like an industry', most visibly under the guise of 'creative industries', failed to cut through to the government. This line of policy advocacy stands as a damaging failure, leaving its value uncertain (see Banks and O'Connor, this issue). Not only has it failed to cut through when needed the most, but the capacity of the cultural sector's research and policy advocacy is now weaker than it was all those years ago, jettisoning critique in the name of 'working with...the ISAs' (ideological state apparatus) at a moment when those ISAs have less and less interest in working with such 'cultural technicians', compliant or otherwise (Bennett, 1992). Contrast with Germany, where the cultural sector could generate rapid statistical and policy responses and high levels of critical policy engagement (Dümcke, this issue).

JobKeeper and Cultural Workers

As has been reported by numerous arts bodies and unions, *JobKeeper* is inadequate for most artists and cultural workers in respect of their meeting the eligibility criteria to access it (Eltham 2020a; MEAA 2020; Anatolitis 2020). It excludes those who do not operate as sole traders as well as those who have not been employed with the same employer for over 12-months. These kinds of exclusions reflect a poor grasp of the employment patterns of artists and cultural workers, who are more likely to be seasonal, freelance, and built around short-term contracts with multiple employers. A recent survey by the MEAA (Media Entertainment and Arts Alliance) has reported that at least 35 percent of its membership are ineligible for the program or have been denied access to both *JobKeeper* and *JobSeeker* (MEAA 2020). This is alarming given that, according to the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS), at least 23.4 percent of the 'Arts and Media Professionals' are classified as 'casual' according to the 'Characteristics of Employment' data (ABS 2020). However, more granular data from ethnographic reports suggest even that figure is under-representative, estimating that it is instead approximately 81 percent of all artists who are not 'salaried employees' (Throsby & Petetskaya 2017: 88). At either end of the scale, the federal government chronically underspend on the arts, both in times of prosperity and peril.

When National Cabinet met on April 9th the Labor Party moved to amend *JobKeeper* legislation to include the many arts workers ineligible for the program due to their irregular working patterns and classifications. This was voted down by the Coalition MPs. Hours later, Arts Minister Paul Fletcher (who had also voted down the amendment) offered a miserly \$27M in federal arts rescue funding – an insignificant amount in comparison to what would constitute actual relief for the sector. This funding was also targeted at regional arts funding and Indigenous culture. While useful, this does not address the ongoing financial precarity of arts and culture workers excluded from financial support payments due to issues around eligibility criteria.

It took over 100 days of the Covid-19 pandemic before the Australian Prime Minister Scott Morrison mentioned the word 'arts' as it related to any meaningful financial support package. While the June 24th announcement of a \$250M Federal Government Arts and Entertainment Package (AEP) sounded *prima facie* like welcome relief after the rather insubstantial earlier \$27M announcement, it remains too little, too late (Jericho

2020). ABS data show that 33 percent of all 'Arts & Recreation Services' have seen their revenue drop by more than 75 percent. There is broad consensus that arts and cultural organisations are not only the 'hardest hit' by the pandemic but will take the longest to recover – if at all. Such claims have been supported by data from the Grattan Institute (2020), and the ABS (2020). Already the live music industry suggests a “conservative estimate” of losses to its part of the performance sector - one having been identified as having the capacity potentially to earn at least a 5 percent share of the global market - at half a billion dollars (Tingle 2020). Whether the broader arts industry can even ever fully recover is yet to be determined.

The AEP is structured into four streams consisting of: \$75M of capital funding to help production and event businesses put on new festivals, concerts, tours and events; \$90M in 'show starter' concessional loans to fund new productions and events that stimulate job creation and economic activity; \$35M in direct financial assistance for Commonwealth-funded arts organisations to get them going again; \$50M fund to assist local screen production (film and television) to be administered by Screen Australia. In an emergency any contribution is helpful. However, the bulk of this 'rescue package' is geared towards offering loans that must be paid back by recipient organisations. Only \$35M of the \$250M package actually offers direct financial support to the arts and cultural workforce. Additionally, much of this support will take months to actually administer. So, while this 'rescue package' will be of assistance to a number of arts organisations, direct help geared towards artists who work in the industry as freelancers and casual remains extremely thin on the ground.

Of great concern is the fact that all grant applications for the AEP are going to be overseen by a 'Creative Economy Taskforce' comprised of government ministers 'in partnership' with the Australia Council; yet how much input the latter will have in the oversight of the awarding of this funding is yet to be seen, as details have not been forthcoming in the six weeks after the announcement (Eltham, 2020c; Tingle 2020). In the light of the opacity of the National Covid-19 Commission (Murphey, 2020; Wilkins, 2020) the lack of information on this is worrying.

Given the recent 'sports rorts' scandal - in which the federal government was discovered advancing large amount of infrastructure grant money to sporting clubs located primarily in Coalition or marginally held electorates in the lead-up to the last election (McKenzie 2020) rather than on the merit of the various club's grant application as determined by the recommendations of Sports Australia – there are good reasons to take a skeptical view of the ways this scheme will be administered. The Coalition government has long since abandoned the 'arm's-length' process of administering funding to the arts via intermediary bodies (Cooke, 2020). Instead of relying solely on expert bodies such as Sports Australia or in this case, the Australia Council, the Coalition government insists on the primacy of ministerial fiat. One result of the 'populist' shift of right-wing parties against 'elites' and 'experts' is to assert the power of the elected executive over non-elected intermediary bodies.

Compared to countries such as Germany (Dümcke, this issue), with well-resourced and respected cultural sector bodies, the equivalents in Australia have been starved of

funding and cowed by the threat of further cuts. Over the last decade, at a national level key representative organisations such as NAVA, the National Association for the Visual Arts, have been de-funded, the Australia Council’s funding and grants programs successively reduced, and the crafts sector in Australia has had no representative national organization since 2011. As with the universities, the Coalition government is happy to display disdain for the arts and cultural sector, the burying of Arts in the ‘super-ministry’, merely par for the course. Prime Minister Morrison, in announcing the (in effect \$35M) support package said ‘it was as much about supporting the tradies who build the stage sets or computer specialists who create the latest special effects, as it is about supporting actors and performers’ (Cooke, 2020) – just in case we forgot.

Federal and State Divides

As ‘the arts’ has faded even further into the background under the tenure of the Coalition since their return to power in 2013, much support and advocacy activity has defaulted to state-based organizations such as the ACDC—Australian Craft and Design Centre—network members Artisan (QLD); Australian Design Centre (NSW); Australian Tapestry Workshop (VIC); Canberra Glassworks (ACT); Central Craft (NT); Craft (VIC); Craft ACT (ACT); Design Tasmania (TAS); Form (WA); Guildhouse (SA); JamFactory (SA); Sturt Gallery and Studios (NSW). They all ride the ‘boom and bust’ cycles of variously supportive state governments. As a result, in the wake of the arrival of Covid-19 and the subsequent lockdown measures, offering financial support for arts and cultural workers, and indeed, admitting that the arts industry was hugely affected, was largely spearheaded by state governments who more tangibly feel the criticisms levelled at them for arts under-funding given their actual proximity to those who are directly affected by such funding choices.

Examining the responses by the various state and territory governments provides a further lens by which to understand the lack of any kind of arts support the federal government offers, both in terms of public rhetoric, as well as in practical economic support. At present various state and territory governments, irrespective of party, have attempted, in differing degrees and successes, to support their local arts and culture sectors in the immediate-term as a response to Covid-19 (see Table 1).

Table 1: State and Territory Government Covid-19 Arts Grants

State (state level political party in brackets)	Type of grant	Value
New South Wales (Lib)		\$56M total
	Rescue and Restart	\$50M
	Screen and Arts rent relief	\$6M
Victoria (Lab)		\$43.1M total
	Arts survival package	\$16.8M
	Relief for state-owned arts & cultural institutions	\$26.3M
Queensland (Lab)		\$33M total
	Arts grants (reallocated)	\$2.5M
	Rent relief & funding	\$8M

	Recovery package	\$22.5M
Western Australia (Lab)		\$15.5M total
	Event cancellation relief	\$5M
	Culture & arts organisations staff retention	\$8M
	Sustainability package	\$2.5M
South Australia (Lib)		\$3.5M total
	Arts grants	\$2.5M
	Music industry support package	\$1M
Tasmania (Lib)		\$3.5M total
	Relief funding	\$1.5M
	In-kind support for loan payment suspensions	\$2M
Australian Capital Territory (Lab)		\$2M total
	Arts grants for new works & arts activities	\$2M
Northern Territory (Lab)		\$2M total
	Arts grants for new works	\$2M

State government funding announcements vary in scale, levels of direct financial support and general understanding of what is a complex sector. In some instances, some of this funding is not new, merely repurposed. It does however at least demonstrate a knowledge that those working within the arts have needed far more help than the federal government has been willing to acknowledge either in public rhetoric or actual financial support.

Party lines at the state level do not reflect the same level of ideological rigidity that currently exists at the federal level when it comes to both funding and valuing artists, art and culture. As a combined effort of approximately \$150M the state governments have essentially matched the federal government \$160M AEP funding allocations (ignoring the \$90M 'concessional loans' as part of the AEP). However, while state governments do seem to be offering more than their federal counterparts (particularly so during the immediate phase of Covid-19 and subsequent lockdown measures from late March), it hardly approaches the amount of funding necessary to either offer a way forward for the arts or for those who comprise its workforce.

The Gendered Impacts on Arts and Cultural Work

In keeping with the power and influence of extractive industries in Australia, the focus of recovery has been rhetorically placed on the 'real economy' (Duke and Wright 2020), in this instance the largely male economy of mining and building. This is despite these sectors largely continuing to operate as per usual (at least up until August and the 'second wave' higher level lockdown measures in Victoria). Thus as of the time of the announcements discussed here, these parts of the economy had not been particularly

impacted by Covid-19 (Ludlow 2020; Zhou 2020; Maine, 2020), unlike the arts and cultural sector. There has long been acknowledgement that the frequently informal, network-based and otherwise precarious work practices underpinning much employment in the arts and creative industries are effectively operating as a barrier to gender, ethnic, class and wider social inclusion in the creative economy (Banks 2017; Connor, Gill and Taylor eds. 2015; Luckman, et al. 2020). Nonetheless, the inequities upon arts and creative employment have disproportionately impacted women, who are more likely than men to be employed casually, part-time or be self-employed (Hill, 2020). Payroll jobs figures released by the Australian Bureau of Statistics in the first days of Victoria's second wave lockdown in early July revealed that in that state "[w]omen, many of whom are on part-time or casual work in areas such as accommodation and the arts, suffered a major hit" falling 0.2 percent for men and 1.1 percent for women (Wright 2020). This is on top of the already substantial losses in creative employment.

Despite the fact that arts and culture has been one of the sectors hardest hit, government stimulus packages have replicated the policy settings already in place prior to the pandemic and continued to privilege the 'blokes in hard hats' parts of the economy. We are seeing a 'pink collar recession' (Ribeiro 2020) as tourism, hospitality, arts, entertainment and culture are all hit particularly hard, resulting in unemployment figures that continue to show women's unemployment has been hit far harder than men's in Australia (Janssens 2020). Making matters worse, these figures only capture a partial picture with even the Treasurer admitting that the official unemployment figure in July was 'more like' 13.3 percent and not the 7.1 percent officially reported (Janssens 2020). Among those missing from this statistical picture are those women who have variously 'chosen' to return to care-giving in the home as their primary focus for the foreseeable future, removing themselves from the paid job market. As schools closed or families elected to keep their children at home, it has largely been women who have wound back their employment hours or otherwise stepped back from the paid workforce to care for them. With high official unemployment figures likely to be with us for a while, it is hard not to think the government is grateful for this reassertion of traditional gender roles; certainly, an affirmation of them is reflected in the economic sectors they have chosen on which to focus stimulus.

Conclusion: Across 'the Ditch', another World is Possible

In terms of support for art and culture New Zealand represents a distinct contrast with Australia. This is not just about the size and speed of the response, though both were far better, but also the quality of engagement with its representations and the sense of public of value within which art and culture were framed.

Leader of a Labor government elected in 2017, Jacinda Ardern also holds the portfolio of Minister for Arts, Culture and Heritage. She made an early announcement on May 28th as the Covid-19 crisis worsened, that an \$175M arts rescue package would be made available in stages beginning in July. This followed on from their more general wage subsidy scheme. This shares some similarities with the Australian *JobKeeper* scheme in that it can only be accessed by those with a registered business, and as such, a number

of New Zealand artists and creative workers did not qualify. Such problems of targeting were common in the UK, Germany and elsewhere, as the papers in this special issue indicate. However, Creative New Zealand (CNZ) announced on March 25th that they would be reallocating \$11.5M and newly adding \$4.5M of funding in emergency relief of grants up to \$10K for individuals or collectives 'experiencing devastating loss of income' (Creative New Zealand 2020, n.p.) in an attempt to help artists in financial hardship. CNZ were also invited to speak with the New Zealand government to determine the best practice and approach for getting funding to artists.

When Ardern made the May 28th announcement she specifically said, 'we know many of our creatives get income from multiple sources and it is an ongoing challenge to piece together the gigs and commissions to earn a livelihood' (1 News, 2020, n.p.). Having a Prime Minister who publicly announces this kind of understanding of the more complex work patterns for artists and creative industries workers has put New Zealand in an, at present, enviable position. While acknowledging that New Zealand's federal government do not have the same state government organizational structures as Australia's owing to their smaller population size, the level of understanding from New Zealand's federal government was notably different from Australia. Employing a policy rhetoric of the arts and culture as an important and valued sector, it displayed a willingness to adapt to their more complex employment patterns absent in Australia.

That it was able to do so reflects the country's continued commitment to an arts and cultural policy. By contrast, Covid-19 has revealed that 'Australia does not have a cultural policy' (Meyrick, et. al. 2020). Or rather, it has a counter-cultural policy, asserting its commitment to 'non-elite' culture and military heritage, whilst leaving Covid-19 to do the work of hollowing out the arts, the ABC/SBS and universities (especially arts and humanities) and public services more generally (Cooke, 2020). This whilst promoting fossil fuels and other extractive industries as the only way forward in a 'business led' recovery (Eltham, 2020). Ardern's government is not averse to the 'art as industry' rhetoric (Banks and O'Connor, this issue) the advocacy around which has been so signally unsuccessful in an Australia which has no industry policy (O'Connor, 2020). However, the broader context for art and culture is framed in terms of 'well-being for all'.

A key part of Prime Minister Jacinda Ardern's pitch to New Zealanders was that there is more to the success of a nation than GDP as a way to measure standards of living, and that her government would tackle issues of poverty, mental health, First Nation's support, and climate change. In this it echoes one of the emerging themes from this dire global emergency, one that links the health crisis to the broader issue of social services, the responsibilities and capacities of the state, and how we understand the purpose of government: care (Care Collective, 2018; Serafini and Novosel, this issue). The 'gendered pandemic' (Hill, 2020) is at the heart of this politics of care, but it is one which cultural sector advocacy in Australia has been slow to grasp. The rhetoric of creativity, innovation and economic growth, in a cultural sector where 'trickle-down economics' is still an article of faith (see Morris (2020) for the music industry), has meant they have so far missed the occasion to articulate a new value for art and culture. Linking an ethics of care to a new sense of the political economy of public value

(Meyrick and Barnett, this issue) and to the specific value of art and culture seems to us the order of the day.

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ⁱ JobSeeker, in the first wave of economic bailout replaced the income support mechanism otherwise known as Newstart which had depending on circumstances, prior to the onset of Covid-19, been paid at a rate of \$565 per fortnight, long been called out as woefully insufficient by the social service sector (ACOSS 2019). Newstart had not seen an increase in real terms in over 20-years, with its recipients being forced to live below the poverty line. Campaigns to 'raise the rate' of Newstart (and Australia's other social support payment Youth Allowance) had been finding much more political traction during 2019, and a Senate inquiry (and report) into the adequacy of such income support mechanisms by the Senate Community Affairs Reference Committee took submissions until September 30th 2019. The report published in April 2020 while highlighting that 'payment rates for jobseekers do not support an acceptable minimum standard of living' (Community Affairs Reference Committee 2020 p159) had yet to see any federal government action as a result. JobSeeker is currently being paid at double the rate of Newstart at \$1100 per fortnight, but uncertainty remains as for how much longer the government will provide this level of income support (a review is currently scheduled for September 2020).

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